

**THE ROLE OF CONTEMPORARY AND TRADITIONAL METHODS IN EFFECTIVE TEACHING
IN THE PRIMARY EDUCATION -STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES**

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Abstract:

Introduction: teaching is a really important process and the methods used are different. Some researchers think that modern teaching has advantages over the traditional one and some think differently.

Objective: This study aims to determine the prevalence of contemporary methods and techniques in the daily work of teachers. It seeks to highlight the most commonly used methods in a teaching hour and identify the most effective methods in a teaching session from a pupils/students' perspective.

Material and Methods To conduct this study, both quantitative (questionnaire) and qualitative (interviews, discussions) methods were employed. Two questionnaires were administered (Questionnaire 1 for teachers and Questionnaire 2 for students), and structured interviews were conducted with school directors, as well as unstructured interviews and discussions with teachers and students from the selected schools. Data were collected from 100 students for Questionnaire 1 and 15 teachers for Questionnaire 2. The study was carried out in three 9-year primary schools in the city of Tirana. The study population included students from the fourth and fifth grades, teachers working in the primary education classes, and the directors of these schools.

Results: Contemporary methods are being practiced in our schools, but it should be noted that our teachers, especially those with many years of experience, still tend to be somewhat traditional in the classroom. The implementation of learner-centered teaching models is essential for contemporary and qualitative education. These findings support the positive correlation between contemporary teaching and educational quality

Keywords: Contemporary methods, traditional methods, educational quality, pupils/students' perspectives

Introduction

The selection and application of teaching methods are central to the effectiveness of classroom instruction, particularly in the lower cycle of education. Traditional approaches such as lecture, demonstration, and text-book-based instruction have provided structure and consistency for decades. However, research increasingly highlights the importance of adopting more contemporary, student-centered approaches that actively engage learners and stimulate motivation. This literature review examines findings from systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and regional reports to analyze the effectiveness of traditional and contemporary methods, their influence on engagement, motivation, and achievement, and the contextual factors shaping their implementation.

Traditional methods of instruction, characterized by teacher-centered delivery, repetition, and reliance on textbooks, continue to dominate in many educational systems. These approaches ensure structured delivery of curricular content and are particularly valued in contexts where resources are limited and standardized outcomes are emphasized. According to OECD (2020), Albanian classrooms often rely on such practices, reflecting systemic traditions and assessment priorities. While effective in maintaining order and transmitting knowledge, these approaches have been criticized for

fostering passive learning and limited opportunities for student autonomy or problem-solving. Bremner et al. (2022), in their systematic review of learner-centered pedagogy, underscore that although teacher-centered methods provide predictability, they often fail to address the developmental needs of younger learners who benefit from interaction and active engagement.

In contrast, contemporary methods—ranging from project-based learning, gamification, and the use of educational technologies to blended and interactive instruction—emphasize learner autonomy and participation. Li et al.'s (2023) meta-analysis on student engagement highlights the critical role of teaching practices that provide feedback, interactivity, and collaborative opportunities in enhancing engagement and intrinsic motivation across K–12 contexts. Similarly, Ashraf et al. (2021), in a systematic review of blended learning, conclude that hybrid methods consistently produce better outcomes than purely traditional approaches, with benefits in student satisfaction, achievement, and motivation.

At the elementary level, systematic reviews focused specifically on blended learning in science education have reported moderate to strong improvements in engagement and conceptual understanding when active and digital elements are integrated with teacher guidance (Halim et. al., 2025). These findings suggest

that contemporary methods are particularly suited to younger learners, who are naturally curious and responsive to interactive experiences.

One of the strongest bodies of evidence for contemporary pedagogical practices concerns formative assessment and feedback. Sortwell et al. (2024), in their umbrella review of meta-analyses, conclude that formative assessment has consistent small-to-large effects on learning outcomes in K–12 education, particularly when implemented through adaptive tasks and constructive feedback. This evidence aligns with Self-Determination Theory, which emphasizes the importance of supporting learner competence, autonomy, and relatedness as drivers of intrinsic motivation. Schildkamp et al. (2020) extend this argument, showing that teachers require adequate training, resources, and time to implement formative assessment effectively. These findings are particularly relevant for lower cycle teaching, where clear feedback and interactive scaffolding are critical for sustaining student engagement.

The relationship between teaching methods and student motivation has been well documented across diverse contexts. Bremner et al. (2022) show that learner-centered methods consistently improve engagement and participation, even in low-resource environments. Li et al. (2023) confirm that interactive and feedback-rich practices are positively associated with intrinsic motivation, while repetitive or passive methods tend to reduce engagement. For younger learners in the lower cycle, motivation is particularly fragile, making the teacher's choice of method a decisive factor. Contemporary methods such as gamification, collaborative projects, and personalized learning approaches appear to create sustained motivation, which in turn supports higher academic performance.

Despite the advantages of contemporary methods, the literature also suggests that a balanced or blended approach may be most effective. Ashraf et al. (2021) emphasize that blending traditional structure with contemporary flexibility yields better results than adopting either approach exclusively. The OECD (2020) report on Albania echoes this, noting that while systemic reliance on traditional methods persists, there is growing recognition of the need to integrate innovative practices that align with students' evolving needs. This suggests that effective teaching in the lower cycle may not involve replacing traditional methods entirely but rather combining them with interactive and feedback-oriented approaches to maximize both structure and engagement.

It is important to acknowledge that the effectiveness of contemporary methods depends on contextual conditions such as teacher preparedness, class size, and access to resources. Schildkamp et al. (2020) caution that formative assessment, while powerful, requires professional development and systemic support to be successful. Similarly, Bremner et al. (2022) note that learner-centered pedagogy is most effective when teachers receive adequate training in facilitating active learning environments. In regions like Albania, where resource constraints and traditional assessment frameworks persist (OECD, 2020), the challenge is to adapt

contemporary methods in ways that are feasible and culturally appropriate.

Overall, the literature demonstrates that while traditional methods provide structure and consistency, they are limited in fostering engagement and motivation, particularly in the lower cycle of education. Contemporary methods, by contrast, support active learning, critical thinking, and intrinsic motivation, leading to improved student outcomes. Evidence from systematic reviews and meta-analyses indicates that blended approaches that integrate traditional and contemporary techniques may offer the greatest benefits. However, the success of these methods depends on teacher preparation, institutional support, and context-sensitive adaptation. For lower cycle teaching, a deliberate and balanced selection of methods appears to be the key to promoting sustainable learning and active student engagement.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection to investigate students' perspectives on teaching methods and classroom engagement. The primary instrument for the study was a questionnaire administered to students, which captured their experiences, opinions, and engagement levels regarding different teaching methods. In addition to the questionnaire, discussions and unstructured interviews were held with students to gain deeper insight into their perceptions and classroom experiences.

Population and Sample

The participants in this study were students from three lower-cycle schools in Tirana: "*Emin Duraku*," "*Skënder Luarasi*," and "*Edith Durham*." A total of 100 students were randomly selected from these schools, comprising 60% fifth-grade and 40% fourth-grade students, aged 10 to 12 years. Regarding gender distribution, 37% of participants were male and 63% female. These students formed the core sample of the study, providing both quantitative data through the questionnaire and qualitative insights through interviews and discussions.

Data Collection

The main tool for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed specifically for this study and another previous study focusing on teachers' perspectives on the use of teaching methods (Aliaj et al., 2025). It consisted of pre-determined, closed-ended questions designed to gather students' perceptions of the effectiveness of traditional and contemporary teaching methods, their engagement in classroom activities, and their motivation for learning. To complement the quantitative data, unstructured interviews and small-group discussions were conducted with students to explore their personal experiences and opinions in greater depth.

All data collection procedures prioritized students' perspectives, focusing on their active participation, engagement, and reflections on learning methods. Two key methods guided the study: theoretical analysis of teaching approaches and practical consultation with students to ensure their experiences were accurately captured.

Graph 1: Results for Survey Question 1

Graph 2: Results for Survey Question 2

Graph 3: Results for Survey Question 3

Graph 4: Results for Survey Question 4

Graph 5: Results for Survey Question 5

Graph 6: Results for Survey Question 6

Graph 7: Results for Survey Question 7

Graph 8: Results for Survey Question 8

Table 1: Summarizing table of percentages per each survey question.

Graph / Indicator	Skender Luarasi (%)	Edith Durham (%)	Emin Duraku (%)	Category / Note
G.1: Method where students feel better	40 / 35 / 25	45 / 30 / 25	50 / 30 / 20	Methods A / B / C
G.2: Freedom to give personal opinion	86 / 14 / 0	90 / 10 / 0	95 / 5 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never
G.3: Use of supplementary tools	45 / 55 / 0	75 / 25 / 0	80 / 20 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never
G.4: Clarity of teacher questions	94 / 6 / 0	100 / 0 / 0	100 / 0 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never
G.5: Consideration of students' opinions	53 / 47 / 0	87 / 13 / 0	97 / 3 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never
G.6: Collaboration with classmates	42 / 56 / 2	93 / 7 / 0	93 / 7 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never
G.7: Students active in lesson	80 / 20 / 0	90 / 10 / 0	95 / 5 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never
G.8: Teaching adapted to student level	88 / 12 / 0	93 / 7 / 0	95 / 5 / 0	Always / Sometimes / Never

Results

The analysis of student responses highlights a clear preference for student-centered teaching methods. According to Graph 1, the majority of students across all three schools reported feeling better during interactive and participatory lessons compared to traditional methods. Students also indicated high levels of freedom to express their opinions (Graph 2), with 86–95% stating they are “always” able to share ideas during lessons. The use of supplementary tools to support learning was perceived positively (Graph 3), with 45–80% of students reporting consistent use depending on the school.

Students reported that teachers communicate clearly (Graph 4), with 94–100% indicating instructions and questions are always understandable. Likewise, the consideration of students' opinions during lessons (Graph 5) ranged from 53% to 97% “always,” showing that classrooms generally value student input. Collaboration with classmates was common (Graph 6), although Skender Luarasi showed slightly lower “always” responses (42%), while other schools reported over 90%. Students also reported being active participants in lessons (Graph 7, 80–95% “always”) and that teachers adapt lessons to their level (Graph 8, 88–95% “always”), indicating differentiation in instruction.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that contemporary teaching methods effectively promote engagement, autonomy, collaboration, clarity, and adaptation to student needs. Differences between schools suggest that implementation may vary depending on context, but the general trend shows that student-centered approaches positively impact lower-cycle students' learning experiences.

Discussions and Conclusions

The findings of this study align closely with the broader theoretical literature on teaching and learning in the lower cycle. As highlighted in prior research (Bremner et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023; Ashraf et al., 2021), student-centered approaches are strongly associated with higher levels of engagement, autonomy, and motivation. The student responses in this study confirm these trends: across all three schools, students

reported feeling better during interactive and participatory lessons, expressing freedom to share opinions, and actively engaging in classroom activities. These results contrast with the limitations of traditional methods, which, while valued for structure and consistency (OECD, 2020), often restrict opportunities for collaboration and self-expression.

The findings of this study confirm the findings of a previous one (Aliaj et al., 2025) and the wider literature show that student-centered and blended methods consistently improve engagement, collaboration, and freedom of expression, fostering critical and creative thinking among younger learners. At the same time, their effectiveness depends on contextual factors such as teacher preparation, school resources, and class conditions, highlighting the need for a balanced and well-supported integration of contemporary and traditional approaches.

The data also support arguments for blended approaches that integrate traditional structure with contemporary flexibility (Ashraf et al., 2021). For example, while teacher clarity and structured guidance were universally appreciated by students (94–100% reported clear instructions), the strongest positive responses were linked to interactive practices such as collaboration with peers, adaptation to student needs, and freedom of opinion. This balance reflects the theoretical claim that contemporary methods are not meant to replace traditional approaches entirely but to enrich them in ways that foster active and inclusive learning environments.

At the same time, the variation observed between schools, particularly in areas such as collaboration (42% “always” at Skender Luarasi vs. over 90% at the other two schools), underscores the role of contextual factors identified in the literature. As Schildkamp et al. (2020) note, the effectiveness of learner-centered and formative approaches depends on adequate teacher preparation, resources, and institutional support. The differences between schools in this study may reflect disparities in training, pedagogical culture, or access to supplementary tools.

In conclusion, both the theoretical literature and the empirical findings point to the same outcome: student-centered and blended teaching methods are more effective than purely traditional approaches in promoting engagement, autonomy, and sustainable learning. For lower-cycle students in Albania, classrooms that value student input, provide opportunities for collaboration, and adapt lessons to individual needs appear to create the most positive learning environments. However, ensuring consistent implementation across schools requires targeted teacher training, resource allocation, and systemic support. A deliberate, context-sensitive balance between traditional and contemporary methods emerges as the most effective path for fostering student motivation and success in the early years of schooling.

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